

Effect of Size and Shape in Non-Polar Liquid Mixtures*

S. N. BHATTACHARYYA, R. C. MITRA & T. GANGULY

Department of Physical Chemistry,
Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Jadavpur, Calcutta-32.

Received 4 September 1972

The general corresponding states theory of Prigogine and coworkers applicable to the thermodynamic properties of mixtures of spherical molecules and polymer solutions, has been extended to the mixtures of non-spherical molecules and polymer solutions having non-spherical segments by using a potential originally due to Rowlinson. The mixing functions are divided into two contributions, central and non-central. The results from the theory are contrasted with Flory and Prigogine theory for several mixtures. For condensed gas mixtures results are similar and non-central interaction is negligible but for other globular mixtures non-central terms are found to be large and important. The theory explains the experimental data well.

Theories of polymer solution thermodynamics and its extension to nonpolar liquid mixtures in general have recently attracted much attention. The theory advanced by Prigogine and his coworkers¹ is a corresponding states approach and can be applied to both polymer solutions and solutions of spherical molecules of near equal size. The work of Flory and his collaborators²⁻⁷ which has been successfully applied to many binary systems should also be specially mentioned in this connection. Recently Patterson and his coworkers⁸ have shown that although Flory^{2,4} suggested that their theory should be independent of cell model, it is in reality a particular case of Prigogine theory with $m = 3$, $n \rightarrow \infty$. Whatever may be the case, we agree with Patterson⁹ that too much importance should not be attached *a priori* to any one of these models. In the present state of development it seems to be more advantageous to formulate first the corresponding states theory of chain molecule liquids and mixtures as prescribed by Prigogine in a general way and then the properties of "reference" liquids or pure liquids, as the case may be, be obtained by using the particular models.

The success of Prigogine corresponding states theory reformulated by Patterson and coworkers⁸⁻¹⁰ or that of Flory and coworkers²⁻⁷ is primarily due to justice done to the size effects. The basic idea inherent in the Prigogine corresponding states principle of polymeric liquids is to divide a molecular chain or a large molecule into potential surfaces each associated with a certain core volume, the potential being of spherical symmetry having a general (m, n) dependence. The thermodynamics is then expressed in terms of the interaction between two different kinds of surfaces present in the mixture. The result obtained is thus

*Dedicated to Prof. Santi R. Palit on the occasion of his 60th birth anniversary.

equivalent to that of a solution consisting of spherical molecules of different sizes. This is manifested in the results obtained for the first order interaction terms (reference 9).

$$G^E : H^E : V^E = -\tilde{U} : -\tilde{U} + \tilde{T}\tilde{C}_p : \tilde{T}\tilde{\partial}\tilde{V}/\tilde{\partial}\tilde{T} \quad \dots (1)$$

The contact interaction term due to Flory is also equivalent to (1). The results of theoretical calculation for the excess thermodynamic functions of non-polymeric mixtures but with moderate size difference are remarkably close for both the Prigogine corresponding states theory with (6, 12) potential and Flory theory (reference 9) due to above reason.

In spite of these greatly refined theories there remain discrepancies with experiments particularly for excess free energy. The latter may well be due to a centrality of the force field around the molecules or polymer segments causing considerable deviation from relation (1). It is difficult to estimate quantitatively the contributions from the orientation effect owing to obvious mathematical difficulties. Many attempts have been made in this direction (references 14 to 25) all of which predict distortion and deviation of the resultant potentials from that of a simple L. J. Potential. Some of the potentials are too complicated and can not be used in a corresponding states approach. There are also treatments based on which a theorem of corresponding states for polyatomic molecules of globular types can be formulated. A crude, arbitrary but a very useful method is to assume a potential suggested by Rowlinson¹⁴⁻²⁶ for a non spherical molecule

$$\epsilon^*(r) = \epsilon^0 \left[\left(\frac{v}{v^0} \right)^{-4} - 2 \left(\frac{v}{v^0} \right)^{-2} \{1 + \alpha g(\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_{12})\} \right] \quad \dots (2)$$

where α is a small parameter and g is a sum of products of surface harmonics, $\epsilon^*(r)$ being the perturbed potential due to the presence of noncentral forces. An average of the angle gives a temperature dependent parameter $\delta(T)$ which is proportional to the square of the coefficients of noncentral terms. One may finally express the potential in the same form as a (6, 12) L. J. Potential replacing v^0 by $v^0[1 - 3\delta(T)]^3$ and ϵ^0 by $\epsilon^0[1 + 2\delta(T)]$. Such a procedure is rather arbitrary when applied to nonspherical molecules or 'segments' of chain molecules. The function g is not specified and hence cannot be estimated from the molecular parameters for a pure liquid. But the potential, as pointed earlier, is conformal with (6,12) L. J. Potential and can be used with advantage in a corresponding states approach. Moreover, in the case of a mixture with the use of the potential (2) one would encounter a parameter Δ_{12} equal to $2(2\delta_{12} - \delta_{11} - \delta_{22})$ neglecting higher order terms^{26,27} which may be estimated from experimental data.

We define the molar configurational quantities of a polyatomic or a chain molecule at constant negligible pressure as (reference 8, 9).

$$\begin{aligned} V(n, T) &= V^* \tilde{V}(\tilde{T}); & V^* &= N.r(n).v^* \\ U(n, T) &= U^* \tilde{U}(\tilde{T}); & U^* &= N.q.(n).e^* \\ S(n, T) &= S^* \tilde{S}(\tilde{T}); & S^* &= N.c(n).k \end{aligned} \quad \dots (3)$$

where ϵ^* and v^* are now functions of temperature. The effective number of segments r , q and c defined in (3) are proportional respectively, as in Prigogine notations, to the molecular volume, molecular surface and external degrees of freedom.

Thermodynamic Properties of Mixing: When discussing mixtures having different sizes and acentricity we shall use molecular "surface fraction" $X_2 = x_2 q_2 / (x_1 q_1 + x_2 q_2)$ used by Prigogine and the 'segment fraction' $\phi_2 = x_2 V_2^* / (x_1 V_1^* + x_2 V_2^*) = \frac{x_2 r_2 v_2^*}{x_1 r_1 v_1^* + x_2 r_2 v_2^*}$ extensively used by Flory. We shall be following Flory that the component molecules constituting the mixture are divided into equal sized "unperturbed segments" so that $v_1^0 = v_2^0$. This division, it may be mentioned in this connection, is rather for convenience only and has no absolute significance. In Prigogine theory, a parameter ρ occurs,

$$\frac{r_2}{r_1} \cdot \frac{v_2^0}{v_1^0} = \frac{r_2}{r_1} (1 + \rho)^3 \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

and with the assumption $v_1^0 = v_2^0$, ρ becomes $\rho = 0$. Along with X_2 , ϕ_2 and $\rho = 0$, we shall use the usual Prigogine parameters θ and δ^* related to the 'unperturbed' molecular scalefactors now of the component molecules and their mixtures

$$\theta = [\epsilon_{12}^0 - \frac{1}{2}(\epsilon_{11}^0 + \epsilon_{22}^0)] / \epsilon_{11}^0; \quad \delta = (\epsilon_{22}^0 / \epsilon_{11}^0) - 1 \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

The average reduced temperature of the mixture is

$$T = \frac{kT}{\langle \epsilon^* \rangle} \left\langle \frac{c}{q} \right\rangle \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

where

$$\left\langle \frac{c}{q} \right\rangle = X_1 \frac{c_1}{q_1} + X_2 \frac{c_2}{q_2} = \frac{x_1 c_1 + x_2 c_2}{x_1 q_1 + x_2 q_2} = \frac{\bar{c}}{\bar{q}}$$

The use of perturbed potential (2) immediately splits any excess function A^E into terms one A_0^E , being the contribution of the central forces and the other A_s^E due to orientational forces arising out of the acentricity of the molecules

$$A^E = A_0^E + A_s^E \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

A_0^E are same as those obtained by Prigogine and coworkers (eqn. 17.6.1, 17.7.1 of reference 1, Ch. XVII)) and may be written explicitly in terms of θ and δ for the case of $\rho = 0$

$$\frac{q_1}{q} G_0^E = 2\theta H_1 X_1 X_2 + \frac{1}{2} T C p_1 [b + (1 - \bar{f}^2)(a - b) - X_2(1 - f^2)/(1 + \delta)] - \frac{q_1}{q} T S_1^E \quad \dots \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{q_1}{q} H_0^E = 2\theta(H_1 - T C p_1) X_1 X_2 - \frac{1}{2} T^2 \frac{dC p_1}{dT} [b + (1 - \bar{f}^2)(a - b) - X_2(1 - f^2)/(1 + \delta)] \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{r_1}{\bar{r}} V_0^E = T \frac{dV_1}{dT} \{ \{a - b\bar{f} - 1\} - \phi_2 \{f/(1 + \delta) - 1\} \} + \frac{1}{2} T^2 \frac{dV_1}{dT} \{ \{\bar{f}d - 1\}^2 - \phi_2 \{f/(1 + \delta) - 1\}^2 \} \quad \dots \quad (10)$$

*This δ is not the same as $\delta(T)$

where $a = 1 - \delta X_2 + \delta^2 X_2^2$; $b = (\delta^2 - 4\theta\delta X_2 - 4\theta^2 X_1 X_2) X_1 X_2$

$$d = 1 - \delta X_2 - 2\theta X_1 X_2; \quad \bar{f} = \frac{\bar{c}}{c_1} \cdot \frac{q_1}{q}; \quad f = \frac{c_2}{c_1} \cdot \frac{q_1}{q_2}$$

The A_s^E are similar to those obtained by Rowlinson^{26,27} with modification owing to the 'segmentation' procedure

$$\frac{q_1}{q} G_s^E = X_1 X_2 (H_1 + \frac{1}{2} RT) \Delta_{12} \quad \dots (11)$$

$$\frac{q_1}{q} H_s^E = X_1 X_2 (2H_1 - TCp_1 + \frac{1}{2} RT) \Delta_{12} \quad \dots (12)$$

$$\frac{r_1}{\bar{r}} V_s^E = X_1 X_2 \left(\frac{1}{2} V_1 + T \frac{dV_1}{dT} \right) \Delta_{12} \quad \dots (13)$$

For the calculation of excess functions we have assumed as first approximation $q_2/q_1 = r_2/r_1$. This is true only for a very large coordination number Z i.e., $Z \rightarrow \infty$ is a quasi-lattice model. For more refined calculations q_2/q_1 and r_2/r_1 should be distinguished. The q_2/q_1 in that case, may be computed by assuming models connected with the geometry of the molecules. The parameters r_2/r_1 and δ have been estimated in our calculations from the reduction parameter V^* and T^* .

$$\frac{V_2^*}{V_1^*} \simeq \frac{r_2}{r_1}; \quad \frac{T_2^*}{T_1^*} \simeq \frac{c_1 q_2}{c_2 q_1} (1 + \delta) \quad \dots (14)$$

The error in the values of r_2/r_1 and δ obtained from the approximate relation (14), we believe, would not exceed a few percent and is well within the limits of tolerance if the errors in the experimental data of the properties of pure components and the uncertainties inherent in the basic assumptions of theoretical models for the calculations of the reduction parameters from experimental data are considered together. The reduction parameters V^* and T^* of the pure components were calculated from the tables of thermal expansion coefficients, molar volumes and isothermal compressibilities using $\tilde{\alpha}$, \tilde{V} or $\tilde{\beta}$ given by a model comprising of (6, 12) L.J. potential and the cell partition function of Hirschfelder and Eyring used by Prigogine and collaborators¹,

$$\tilde{U} = -2\tilde{V}^{-2} + \tilde{V}^{-4} \quad \dots (15)$$

As shown by Patterson⁸ these are

$$3(\tilde{\alpha}\tilde{T})^{-1} = -6 + \frac{6}{\tilde{V}^2 - 1} + \frac{b\tilde{V}^{-1/3}}{1 - b\tilde{V}^{-1/3}} \quad \dots (16)$$

$$(\beta U^*/V^*)^{-1} = (\tilde{\alpha}\tilde{T})^{-1} [4\tilde{V}^{-1}(\tilde{V}^{-2} - \tilde{V}^{-4})] \quad \dots (17)$$

$$\tilde{T} = 4\tilde{V}^{-2}(1 - \tilde{V}^{-2})(1 - b\tilde{V}^{-1/3}) \quad \dots (18)$$

obtained from the equation of state

$$\frac{\tilde{P}\tilde{V}}{\tilde{T}} = (1 - b\tilde{V}^{-1/3})^{-1} - 4(\tilde{V}^{-4} - \tilde{V}^{-2}) \quad \dots \quad (19)$$

where b is a packing factor, given by $b = 2^{-1/6}$.

The values of θ and Δ_{12} were determined by fitting eqns. (8.11) and (9.12) to the experimental G^E and H^E respectively. V^E was then calculated using these θ and Δ_{12} . TS_1^E in eqn. (8) represents the combinatorial contribution to TS^E and has been estimated from Flory-Huggins combinatorial entropy of mixing using volume fractions. Results for ten systems including some mixtures of spherical molecules have been given in Table 1. The contributions from central and non-central forces have been separately shown for our calculations. Results of calculation using (3, ∞) potential or Flory theory and (6, 12) potential or Prigogine smoothed potential model as reformulated by Patterson and coworkers⁹ have also been listed for comparison in the order of our calculation, (3, ∞) and (6-12).

Table 1 shows that for mixtures of condensed gas molecules and so-called spherical molecules, contributions of non-central forces, as expected, are very small (i.e., $\Delta_{12} \simeq 0$). Noncentral forces are either absent as in the cases of condensed gas molecules or the effect from these forces are mutually cancelled as in the case of $C_6H_6 + CCl_4$ system. The latter is in reality a mixture of globular molecules. Results, for the above systems are almost identical with those of the (3, ∞) model or the (6, 12) Prigogine model and particularly with the latter. But for other mixtures of non-spherical molecules our theory predicts substantial contributions from non-central forces and very well interpret the experimental data of these systems. The more or less identical results obtained by us for mixtures of spherical molecules with Flory and Prigogine theory to some extent justifies our first approximation $q_2/q_1 = r_2/r_1$ for mixtures of molecules with moderate size difference. The errors introduced in \tilde{T} of the mixtures from first approximation and the error in the estimation of δ due to approximate nature of (14) have been compensated by the experimental fit of θ , free volume contributions being small for these systems. However for mixtures of chain molecules, where free volume contributions are large, the first approximation would affect the results and q and r should be distinguished. It may be pointed out, in this connection, that we have chosen the use of the explicit eqns. (8-10) for the sake of straightforward calculations. The Prigogine eqns. (8-10) were obtained by expanding \tilde{T} around \tilde{T}_{11} of one of the components. The series thus obtained is slower to converge and δ over a certain magnitude is not permitted for good results. δ -values above the prescribed limit, if used, might give absurd results. The expansion used by Patterson⁹, in this regard, is certainly superior. One may, as well, use Patterson eqns. for (6-12) potential (eqns, 16, 17, ref. 9) for A_0^E .

Acknowledgements : We gratefully acknowledge the financial support of C.S.I.R., India for R.C.M. and T.G. Thanks are due to Prof. S. R. Palit, Head of the Physical Chemistry Department, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Calcutta, India.

TABLE I
Central and Non-Central Contributions for the equimolar mixtures

System	Experimental							Theoretical					θ	Δ_{12}	$t^\circ\text{C}$
	H^E cal mole ⁻¹	G^E cal mole ⁻¹	V^E cm ³ mole ⁻¹	H^E_0 cal mole ⁻¹	H^E_s cal mole ⁻¹	G^E_0 cal mole ⁻¹	G^E_s cal mole ⁻¹	G^E cal mole ⁻¹	V^E_0 cm ³ mole ⁻¹	V^E_3 cm ³ mole ⁻¹	V^E cm ³ mole ⁻¹				
$\text{O}_2 + \text{A}$	14	9	0.14	12.9	1.1	8.6	0.4	9.0	0.05	0.01	0.06	-0.0116	-0.0012	-189	
$\text{A} + \text{N}_2$	12	8	-0.18	15.6	-3.6	9.4	-1.4	8.0	-0.07	-0.03	-0.10	-0.0133	0.0041	-189	
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_6 + \text{CCl}_4$	27	20	0.01	35.7	-8.7	23.3	-3.3	20.0	0.10	-0.04	0.06	-0.0060	0.0018	25	
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12} + \text{CCl}_4$	35	17	0.16	11.0	24.0	8.0	9.0	17.0	0.04	0.12	0.16	-0.002	-0.0055	25	
$\text{C}_8\text{H}_6 + \text{C}_6\text{H}_{10}$	129.3	65	0.32	70.4	58.9	42.4	22.6	65.0	0.13	0.24	0.37	-0.0135	-0.0123	25	
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_6 + \text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}$	192.5	77	0.65	9.3	183.2	6.8	70.2	77.0	0.01	0.75	0.76	-0.0021	-0.0355	25	
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_6 + n\text{-C}_6\text{H}_{14}$	205	76	0.46	55.0	150.0	18.6	57.4	76.0	-0.15	0.61	0.46	-0.0203	-0.0270	25	
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_6 + n\text{-C}_7\text{H}_{16}$	225	83	0.62	-13.0	238.0	-8.2	91.2	83.0	-0.10	0.97	0.87	-0.0058	-0.0408	25	
$\text{C}_8\text{H}_{12} + n\text{-C}_6\text{H}_{14}$	51	17	0.15	35.8	15.4	11.2	5.8	17.0	-0.10	0.10	0	-0.0066	-0.0031	20	
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12} + n\text{-C}_7\text{H}_{16}$	64	0	0.30	-85.0	149.0	-56.5	56.5	0	-0.32	0.76	0.44	0.0125	-0.0281	20	

N O T A T I O N S

- a = Substitute in eqns. (8) to (10)
 A^E = A typical thermodynamic excess function.
 A^{E_0} = Excess function due to central forces.
 A^{E_s} = Excess function due to non-central forces.
 b = Packing factor.
 c = Number of external degrees of freedom of a molecule.
 \bar{c} = Averaged value of c with respect to molefraction.
 C_p = Molar specific heat at constant pressure.
 \tilde{C}_p = Reduced value of C_p .
 $\left\langle \frac{c}{q} \right\rangle$ = Ratio of $\bar{c} : \bar{q}$
 d = Substitute in equn. (10)
 f = Substitute in equns. (8) to (10)
 \bar{f} = Value of f corresponding to \bar{c} and \bar{q}
 g = Spherical harmonics
 G^E = Excess Gibbs free energy
 G^{E_0} = Excess Gibbs free energy due to central forces.
 G^{E_s} = Excess Gibbs free energy due to non-central forces.
 H_1 = Molar enthalpy
 H^E = Molar Excess Enthalpy
 H^{E_0} = Molar Excess enthalpy due to central forces.
 H^{E_s} = Molar Excess enthalpy due to non-central forces.
 k = Boltzmann's constant.
 m, n = Exponents in the bi-reciprocal Lennard-Jones Potential
 \tilde{P} = Reduced Pressure.
 q = Molecular surface associated with a segment.
 q_i = Molecular surface associated with a segment of i -th species.
 \bar{q} = Averaged value of q with respect to molefraction.
 r = Number of segments of a molecule.
 \bar{r} = Number of segments of the i -th component.
 R = Universal gas constant.
 S = Entropy function.
 S^E = Excess Entropy.
 S^{E_1} = Combinatory excess entropy.
 t = Temperature of the mixture in °C.
 T = Absolute temperature.

\tilde{T}	=	Reduced value of T
\tilde{T}_{ij}	=	Reduced temperature of the ij molecule pair.
T_i^*	=	Characteristic temperature of the i -th component.
v	=	Molar volume.
v^0	=	Characteristic core volume.
v_i^*	=	Characteristic volume of the i -th component.
V^E	=	Molar Excess volume.
V_i^*	=	Characteristic molar volume of the i -th component.
\tilde{V}	=	Reduced molar volume.
X_i	=	Molecular surface fraction.

Greek Letters :

α	=	Asphericity Parameter.
$\tilde{\alpha}$	=	Reduced value of the thermal expansivity
β	=	Isothermal compressibility.
$\tilde{\beta}$	=	Reduced value of β
θ	=	Normalised deviation of the intermolecular potential of a unlike pair from the arithmetic mean of the like pairs.
θ_i, θ_{ij}	=	Orientalional quantities in equation (2).
ρ	=	Ratio of characteristic length parameters of two unlike molecular species minus unity.
ϕ_i	=	Volume fraction of the i -th component.
δ	=	Ratio of characteristic potential parameters of two unlike molecular species minus unity.
δ_{ij}	=	Value of δ for an (ij) molecular pair.
$\Delta_{1,2}$	=	Structural parameter.
ϵ^*	=	Perturbed potential due to the presence of orientational forces.
ϵ^0	=	Characteristic potential parameter of a molecular species.

Subscripts and Superscripts

E	=	Excess function.
\sim	=	Reduced quantity
i	=	i -th component.
ij	=	ij pair or mixture.
- or $\langle \rangle$	=	Molefractionwise averaged quantity.
*	=	Characteristic molecular quantity.
o	=	Central part of a thermodynamic excess function.
s	=	Structural part of a thermodynamic excess function.

REFERENCES

1. I. Prigogine (with collaboration of A. Bellemens and V. Mathot), *Molecular Theory of Solutions*, North Holland, Amsterdam, 1957; Chapters IX, X, XVI, XVII.
2. P. J. Flory, R. A. Orwoll and A. Vrij, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 3507, 3515.
3. P. J. Flory, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 1833.
4. A. Abe and P. J. Flory, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 1838.
5. R. A. Orwoll and P. J. Flory, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 6814.
6. B. E. Eichinger and P. J. Flory, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1968, **64**, 2053.
7. H. Höcker and P. J. Flory, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1968, **64**, 1188.
8. D. Patterson, S. N. Bhattacharyya and P. Pieker, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1968, **64**, 648.
9. D. Patterson and G. Delmas, *Discuss. Faraday Soc.*, 1970, **49**, 98.
10. D. Patterson, *Macromol.*, 1969, **2**, 672.
11. P. J. Flory, *Discuss. Faraday Soc.*, 1970, **49**, 7.
12. *ibid.*, 1970, **49**, 173.
13. D. Patterson, *Discuss. Faraday Soc.*, 1970, **49**, 173.
14. T. Kihara, *Rev. Mod. Phys.*, 1953, **25**, 531.
15. S. D. Hamann and J. A. Lambert, *Austral. J. Chem.*, 1954, **7**, 1.
16. K. S. Pitzer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 3427.
17. K. S. Pitzer, D. Z. Lippmann, R. F. Curl, C. M. Huggins and D. E. Petersen, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 3433.
18. G. Thomaes, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1952, **49**, 323.
19. M. Atoji and W. N. Lipscomb, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1953, **21**, 1480.
20. J. S. Rowlinson, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1952, **20**, 337.
21. J. S. Rowlinson, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1954, **50**, 647.
22. N. Trappeniers, *Physica*, 1951, **17**, 501.
23. N. Trappeniers, *Ac. Roy. Belg. Cl. Sc. Mem. Fasc.*, 1952, **10**.
24. S. D. Hamann, W. J. MacManamey and J. F. Pearse, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1953, **48**, 351.
25. R. Balescu, *Physica*, 1956, **22**, 224.
26. J. S. Rowlinson, "Liquids and Liquid Mixtures", Butterworths Co. Ltd., London, 1959.
27. S. N. Bhattacharyya, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1967, **41**, 579.

